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Some Experiments with Ensembles of Neural Networks for Classification of Hyperspectral Images*

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Abstract. A hyperspectral image is used in remote sensing to identify different type of coverts on the Earth surface. It is composed of pixels and each pixel consist of spectral bands of the electromagnetic reflected spectrum. Neural networks and ensemble techniques have been applied to remote sensing images with a low number of spectral band per pixel (less than 20). In this paper we apply different ensemble methods of Multilayer Feedforward networks to images of 224 spectral bands per pixel, where the classification problem is clearly different. We conclude that in general there is an improvement by the use of an ensemble. For databases with low number of classes and pixels the improvement is lower and similar for all ensemble methods. However, for databases with a high number of classes and pixels the improvement depends strongly on the ensemble method.

1 Introduction

A hyperspectral image is used in remote sensing (RS) to identify different type of coverts of the Earth surface. One image is formed of pixels of spatial resolution like a normal image, but in this case each pixel is composed of spectral bands of the electromagnetic spectrum registered by a sensor.

There is a division between multispectral and hyperspectral images in RS, if the number of spectral bands of each pixel in the image is less than 20 the image is called multispectral, otherwise (more than 20 bands) the image is called hyperspectral. The limit is 20 bands, but usually a hiperspectral image has more than 200 bands, as it is the case of the images captured by the sensor AVIRIS which are used in this research.

One of the problems of processing RS images is the supervised classification of pixels. This problems consist on classifying the different pixels into a set of different surface covering, given a known classification of part of the pixels.

The problem of classification of RS images has traditionally been performed by classical statistical methods. However, recently other techniques like neural networks (NN), in particular Multilayer Feedforward (MF) have been applied [1].

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Beside that, it is well known that one technique to increase the performance with respect to a single NN is the design of an ensemble of NNs, i.e., a set of NNs with different initialization or properties in training and combine the different outputs in a suitable and appropriate manner.

This technique has also been applied in the classification of remote sensing images. For example in [2], it is used a simple ensemble of MF networks with the fuzzy integral as combination method. Finally in [3], an ensemble of NNs is used for the estimation of chlorophyll.

However, in the experiments cited above multispectral images (with less than 20 spectral bands) are used and it is rare in the bibliography the utilization of hyperspectral images.

Obviously the problem of classification is different when using a multispectral or a hyperspectral image. In the case of a multispectral image, we will have a NN with less than 20 inputs, which is a normal number of inputs. However, in the case of a hyperspectral image we will have big NNs with around 220 inputs. The results can not be extrapolated for one case to the other.

In this paper we present experiments of eight different methods of constructing the ensembles of MF networks and with four hyperspectral images as data.

The output combination method employed was in all cases *output averaging*, other methods will be tried in future research.

2 Theory

In this section we briefly review the different ensemble methods.

2.1 Simple Ensemble

A simple ensemble can be constructed by training different networks with the same training set, but with different random weight initialization.

2.2 Bagging

This ensemble method is described in reference [4]. It consists on generating different datasets drawn at random with replacement from the original training set. After that, we train the different networks in the ensemble with these different datasets.

2.3 Boosting

This ensemble method is reviewed in [5]. It is conceived for a ensemble of only three networks. The first network is trained with the whole training set. After this training, we pass all patterns through the first network and construct the new training set with 50% of patterns incorrectly classified and 50% correctly classified. With this new training set we train the second network. After that, the original patterns are presented to both networks. If the two networks disagree in the classification, we add the training pattern to the third training set. Otherwise we discard the pattern.

2.4 CVC

It is reviewed in [6]. In *k-fold cross-validation*, the training set is divided into k subsets. Then, $k-1$ subsets are used to train the network. Similarly, by changing the subset that is left out of the training process, one can construct k classifiers, each of which is trained on a slightly different training set. This is the technique used in this method.

2.5 Adaboost

We have implemented the algorithm denominated “Adaboost.M1” in the reference [7]. In the algorithm the successive networks are trained with a training set selected at random from the original training set, but the probability of selecting a pattern changes depending on the correct classification of the pattern and on the performance of the last trained network.

2.6 Decorrelated (Deco)

This ensemble method was proposed in [8]. It consists on introducing a penalty term added to the error function. The penalty term for network number j in the ensemble is:

$$Penalty = \lambda \cdot d(i, j)(y - f_i) \cdot (y - f_j) \quad (1)$$

Where λ is a parameter, y is the target and f_i and f_j are the outputs of networks i and j in the ensemble. The term $d(i, j)$ is 1 for $i=j-1$ and 0 otherwise.

2.7 Decorrelated2 (Deco2)

It was proposed also in reference [8]. It is basically the same method of “Decorrelated” but with a different term $d(i, j)$. In this case $d(i, j)$ is 1 when $i=j-1$ and i is even.

3 Experimental Results

The four hyperspectral images are extracted from two scenes obtained from the *AVIRIS imaging spectrometer*, we describe the scenes in the following paragraphs.

Indian Pines 1992 Data: This data consist of a 145×145 pixels by 224 bands of reflectance data with about two-thirds agriculture and on-third forest or other natural perennial vegetation. Since the scene is taken in June some of the crops present, corn, soybeans, are in the early stages of growth with less than 5% coverage. The ground truth available is designated in sixteen classes and is not all mutually exclusive. From this scene following other experiments [9] and with the intention of comparing the results with the technique of *support vector machines*, we have used two images: the full scene (denominated PINES in our experiments) for which there is a ground truth covering 49% of the scene and it is divided among 16 classes ranging in size from 20 to 2468 pixels, and a subset of the full scene (denominated SUB_PINES in our experiments) consisting of pixels $[27 - 94] \times [31 - 116]$. For this subscene there is a ground truth for

over 75% and it is comprised of the three row crops, Corn-notill, Soybean-notill, Soybean-mintill, and Grass-Trees. Following other works we have reduced the number of bands to 200 by removing the region of water absorption.

Salinas 1998 Data: This scene was acquired on October 9, 1998, just south of the city of Greenfield in the Salinas Valley in California. This data includes bare soils (with five subcategories), vegetables (broccoli with two subcategories, romaine lettuce with 4 subcategories, celery and corn_senesced and green weeds) and vineyards fields (with three subcategories). For a more detailed description of the subcategories see reference [9]. From this scene two images are extracted. The first one (denominated Sal_A in our experiments) comprising 86 x 83 pixels which include the six classes. The second image (denominated Sal_C in our experiments) comprising 217 x 512 pixels which includes the 16 classes described above.

In table 1, there is a brief description of the databases, the columns “Ninput” and “Noutput” are the number of inputs and number of classes in the image respectively. And columns “Ntrain”, “Ncross”, and “Ntest” are the number of pixels included in the training set, cross-validation set and testing set respectively. Also we have a column headed “Nhidden” which contains the optimal number of hidden units for a Multilayer Feedforward network.

Table 1. General characteristics of the images and networks

Database	Ninput	Nhidden	Noutput	Ntrain	Ncross	Ntest
PINES	200	50	16	6633	1658	2075
SUB_PINES	200	15	4	2812	703	878
SAL_A	224	4	6	3423	855	1070
SAL_C	224	36	16	34644	8660	10825

We trained ensembles of three and nine networks. We kept the number of networks in the ensemble low because of the computational cost. We repeated the process of training an ensemble two times with different partitions of data in training, crossvalidation and test sets. In this way, we can obtain a mean performance of the ensemble for each database (the mean of the two trials) and an error in the performance calculated by standard error theory. The results of the performance are in table 2 for the case of ensembles of three networks and in table 3 for the case of nine. We have also included the mean performance of a single network for comparison.

The results of table 2 show that in general there is an improvement by the use of an ensemble except in the case of *Boosting*. The improvement depends on the method and database. The database with lower improvement is SUB_PINES. In the case of database SAL_A the improvement of the ensemble is more or less regular for all ensemble methods. Finally, in databases PINES and SAL_C the improvement is low for some methods and high for others, it seems that the methods which modify the training set (*Adaboost*, *Bagging* and *CVC*) are the best in the case of database SAL_C, and the methods with penalty in the error function (*Decorrelated* and *Decorrelated2*) and the *Simple Ensemble* are the best in database PINES.

As a conclusion, it seems that we can get an increased performance in images of a higher number of pixels and classes, like PINES and SAL_C, but there is no a clear candidate among the different ensemble methods.

Table 2. Results for the ensemble of three networks

	PINES	SUB_PINES	SAL_C	SAL_A
Single Network	91.0 ± 0.2	96.27 ± 0.16	86.03 ± 0.15	99.07 ± 0.19
Adaboost	91.42 ± 0.10	96.0 ± 0.3	95.1 ± 0.2	99.48 ± 0.14
Bagging	92.77 ± 0.10	95.9 ± 0.3	95.9 ± 0.4	99.57 ± 0.14
Boosting	90.5 ± 0.7	95.05 ± 0.06	86.1 ± 0.7	98.0 ± 0.2
CVC	91.5 ± 0.7	96.0 ± 0.5	94.79 ± 0.018	99.48 ± 0.05
Decorrelated	93.3 ± 0.7	96.30 ± 0.17	86.5 ± 0.2	99.39 ± 0.14
Decorrelated2	93.5 ± 0.3	96.7 ± 0.3	86.4 ± 0.2	99.39 ± 0.14
Simple Ensemble	93.63 ± 0.19	96.2 ± 0.4	86.6 ± 0.3	99.43 ± 0.09

Table 3. Results for the ensemble of nine networks

	PINES	SUB_PINES	SAL_C	SAL_A
Single Network	91.0 ± 0.2	96.27 ± 0.16	86.03 ± 0.15	99.07 ± 0.19
Adaboost	92.53 ± 0.10	96.46 ± 0.00	95.90 ± 0.18	99.57 ± 0.04
Bagging	93.54 ± 0.3	96.0 ± 0.3	96.3 ± 0.2	99.67 ± 0.14
CVC	93.3 ± 0.3	96.5 ± 0.6	96.4 ± 0.3	99.62 ± 0.09
Decorrelated	93.7 ± 0.7	96.5 ± 0.3	86.5 ± 0.2	99.48 ± 0.05
Decorrelated2	94.0 ± 0.3	96.8 ± 0.5	86.5 ± 0.3	99.48 ± 0.14
Simple Ensemble	94.53 ± 0.07	96.2 ± 0.5	86.6 ± 0.2	99.48 ± 0.14

By comparing the results of tables 2 and 3, we can see that there is a general improvement by increasing the number of networks in the ensemble. The method which has the highest increasing in performance is *CVC*. In the rest the improvement is usually less than 1%. However, as a trade off the computational cost is greater, which is an important factor to take into account. For example the training time of a neural networks for database PINES was six days in a Pentium 4 processor at 2,4Ghz.

As mentioned before these four images have been used in the reference [9] and we reproduce in table 4 the results of classification with *support vector machines*.

Table 4. Results of using support vector machines (SVM), comparison with other methods

	PINES	SUB_PINES	SAL_C	SAL_A
SVM	87.3	95.9	89	99.5
Single NN	91.0 ± 0.2	96.27 ± 0.16	86.03 ± 0.15	99.07 ± 0.19
Best Ensemble of 9 NNs	94.53 ± 0.07	96.8 ± 0.5	96.4 ± 0.3	99.67 ± 0.14

As shown in table 4 a single NN is a useful alternative to a *SVM*, it performs better in databases PINES and SUB_PINES and worse in SAL_C and SAL_A. We have also included the best results of an ensemble of 9 NNs, as we can see if we select the ensemble methods appropriately we can outperform a single NN and a SVM. The improvement seems to be more important in images with a higher number of pixels and classes, and therefore more difficult to classify.

4 Conclusions

In this paper we have presented experimental results of eight methods of constructing an ensemble of Multilayer Feedforward networks in the application area of hyperspectral image classification. For these experiments we have used a total of four images extracted from two scenes. The results show that in general there is an improvement by the use of an ensemble except in the case of *Boosting*. The improvement depends on the method and database. In databases with a low number of classes and pixels like SUB_PINES and SAL_A (where the general performance of a single network is high) the improvement of the ensemble is lower and more or less regular for all ensemble methods. But, for databases with higher number of pixels and classes like PINES and SAL_C the improvement is low for some methods and high for others, it seems that the methods which modify the training set (*Adaboost*, *Bagging* and *CVC*) are the best in the case of database SAL_C, and the methods with penalty in the error function (*Decorrelated* and *Decorrelated2*) and the *Simple Ensemble* are the best in database PINES. It can be an interesting research to try both alternatives in new application images. Furthermore, we have reproduced the results of *support vector machines* for these images and we have seen that a neural network is an interesting alternative, specially in the case of constructing an appropriate ensemble with several networks.

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